

Supplemental Material

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Table S1. Search Terms

1	kidney transplant*
2	renal transplant*
3	1 or 2
4	sodium glucose transporter 2 inhibitor*
5	sodium glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitor*
6	SGLT-2 inhibitor*
7	SGLT2 inhibitor*
8	SGLT-2i
9	Canagliflozin
10	Dapagliflozin
11	Empagliflozin
12	Ertugliflozin
13	Ipragliflozin
14	Licogliflozin
15	Remogliflozin
16	Sergliflozin
17	4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16
18	3 and 17
19	limit 18 to humans
20	remove duplicates from 19

Table S2. Risk of bias summary for included RCT

		Risk of bias domains					
		D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Study	Halden et al. (2019)						
Domains:		D1: Bias arising from the randomization process. D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention. D3: Bias due to missing outcome data. D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome. D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.					Judgement
							Low

Table S3.

Graph and summary of Risk of Bias in Non-randomized Studies – of Interventions (ROBIN-I) for included non-randomized controlled studies

Study	Risk of bias domains							Overall
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	
Schwaiger et al. (2019)	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
Hisadome et al. (2021)	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Lim et al. (2022)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Demir et al. (2023)	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Mahmoud et al. (2023)	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
Lim et al. (2024)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Domains:

D1: Bias due to confounding.

D2: Bias due to selection of participants.

D3: Bias in classification of interventions.

D4: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions.

D5: Bias due to missing data.

D6: Bias in measurement of outcomes.

D7: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement

- Moderate

+ Low

Figure S4. Funnel Plots of Standard Error on Kidney-Related Outcomes

Figure S5. Funnel Plots of Standard Error on Metabolic Profiles

A. Mortality

Figure S6. Funnel Plots of Standard Error on All-Cause Mortality and Cardiovascular Diseases

Figure S7. Funnel Plots of Standard Error on Adverse Events